

Maximum Entropy and Resistance Balance in Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 2, 2023

Classical statistical mechanics often utilizes the idea of maximizing entropy subject to a physical constraint. For example, for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, this constraint is $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$ where $e_i = p^2/2m$ (no $V(x)$). We have argued previously that there may be many possible constraints, i.e. an average of any power of e_i could be a physical constraint. We stated that a conserved quantity associated with interactions present (creating equilibrium) should be used. Here we examine the constraint in terms of mechanical resistance i.e. pressure.

We further consider the free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ in terms of resistances in time and space. We argue that the form $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ removes the stochasticity associated with motion due to the resistance (impulse) p . Thus 1 or $1/L$ (L =length) seems to be a smoothed over picture associated with a constant flux and overlooks the inherent stochasticity associated with motion. This stochasticity is crucial when describing impulse hit reactions (n -slits, index of refraction interfaces, interactions with $V(x)$), but if a particle does not interact in space, then the $W^*(x)W(x)$ picture seems to be used to describe the $v(\text{average})=x/t$ scenario. The issue is that for a quantum bound state, there is also an rms velocity based on a wavefunction and one may create an average $W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ is real for a bound state), but like $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$, this bypasses some of the stochasticity in the problem, we argue. It only demonstrates stochasticity associated with differences in momentum.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The Maxwell-Boltzmann factor may be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ subject to the physical constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$. This average (or first moment) is said to follow from easing the microcanonical constraint of a fixed total energy. The constraint seems to follow from the characterization given in the microcanonical ensemble. From a math point of view, however, any function $G(e_i)$ should represent a constraint, but what does $G(e_i)$ have to do with the physical problem? We suggest one should use a conserved quantity associated with interactions which create equilibrium in the first place. Here we argue that equilibrium is based on some kind of mechanical balance, at least in the case of problems like an MB gas or the time-independent Schrodinger equation. As a result, we examine how such a mechanical balance influences the constraint used.

It may be noted that for any $G(e)P(e_i)$ used as a constraint, one obtains a certain $P(e_i)$ which may then be used to calculate average pressure:

$$\text{Average}(\text{constant } pv) = \text{Average Pressure } ((1))$$

This pressure exists at all x points and so there is mechanical equilibrium, but each $G(e_i)$ choice yields a different $P(e_i)$ and a different pressure value. If one considers the source of pressure, however, it is linked with collisions of particles. These collisions are based on $P(e_i)$. Thus a collision: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ has a probability $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)P(e_4)$ so that there is time reversal balance. We argue that $e_i = p^2/2m$ is proportional to pressure for the single particle so that a

time reversal balance also ensures that pressure does not change for each interaction. As a result, we argue that energy balance ensures pressure balance which is required for equilibrium. As a result, $\ln(P(e_i))$ adjusts itself to equal e_i which is proportional to the pressure of a single particle. The Lagrange multiplier is $-1/T$, where T is temperature and also happens to be the average pressure of a particle in the system. The maximization of entropy subject to a constraint seems to be closely linked to mechanical pressure balance. Taking d/de of the maximized entropy shows the probability flux linked with mechanical pressure T (per particle):

$$dP(e)/de T = -P(e) \quad ((2))$$

The maximization of \ln of arrangements yields the form:

$$\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) \rightarrow P \ln(P) \quad ((3)),$$

but it is the constraint, linked to mechanical balance which is also crucial to the problem. The form ((2)) is perhaps more readily recognizable in the case of a potential, i.e. From maximizing $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to $-V(x)P(x)/T$. This yields:

$$dP/dx T = -dV/dx P \quad ((4))$$

which is the common pressure-force balance expression in an MB gas.

As a result, we suggest that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint may be partly based on understanding the physical resistance in a problem, with the Lagrange multiplier linked to the resistance.

We stress that pressure is a type of resistance which depends on p and v i.e. $p \cdot v$. It is thus consistent with $x(t)$ in Newtonian mechanics. We suggest in the next section that there may be resistance not directly associated with space and time, for example $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$. Different speeds exist, but the same impulse is given. If one only considers a single impulse hit by one particle, the result does not depend on v even though it occurs at different times for v_1 and v_2 . Unless these times are relevant for the overall problem, it seems they may be ignored.

Quantum Free Particle

We have suggested previously (1), that for a quantum free particle, there are two kinds of resistances, inertia and impulse (momentum). We suggested maximizing Shannon's entropy for both with respect to time and x i.e.

$$\text{Maximize: } -P(x) \ln(P(x)) + i p x P(x) \rightarrow \exp(ipx) \quad ((5a)) \text{ and}$$

$$\text{Maximize } -P(t) \ln(P(t)) - i E t P(t) \rightarrow \exp(-iEt) \quad ((5b))$$

We use different signs for E and p so that $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$ leave $-Et + px$ unchanged. "i" is used to ensure periodicity. In this case, E and p represent resistances associated with free motion, there is no need to consider a reaction. Unlike the reaction picture for which the Lagrange multiplier is $1/T$ where T is average pressure of a particle, here p and E ,

resistance appear in the numerator of the Lagrange multiplier. $\exp(ipx)$ nevertheless applies when there are direct impulse hits. In such a case, one may not need information about velocity as is shown in a later section

We wish to examine these resistances in more detail. A particle with momentum delivers an impulse hit to a target, which may be measured. This is a spatial result because two particles with the same momentum $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ yield the same impulse, but travel through space-time at different rates. Simply recording the strength of impulse hits does not distinguish between the two, but if one also considers time, there is a difference. We note that a particle has momentum because it is moving. What happens if one is in a frame moving at the same constant v as the particle? (Here v is a kind of average $= x/t$). In such a case, the particle does not have momentum and so does not represent an impulse. Does this mean that resistance disappears? We argue it does not because the rest mass represents inertia. Thus there seems to be a resistance in time due to rest mass. When the particle moves (is subject to a force), there is an enhanced inertia, i.e. energy, as well as a momentum. Two resistances appear, one associated with time and the other with space. If one takes the maximization of entropy subject to a constraint followed by a derivative as a balance equation and links this to mechanical resistance, then for a rest mass, t must appear in a linear form in the constraint leading to:

$$d/dt \ln(P(t)) = -iE \quad ((6)) \text{ or } \exp(-iEt)$$

We argue that the probability should hold as seen from different frames moving at constant average speed x/t . Then:

$$-Et = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((7a))$$

In other words, one has the transformation of special relativity.

Maximization of Shannon's Entropy Subject to Momentum Constraint

Above, we maximized $P(x)$ subject to an $i p x P(x)$ constraint. These means the same constraint holds for $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ (nonrelativistically) i.e. for different times. In classical physics, one usually seeks $x(t)$ (i.e. space and time together), but there are problems which do not require time for their solution. For example, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ cause the same damage to a target even though they reach the target at the different times. Similarly, in quantum mechanics, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ create the same n-slit interference-diffraction result albeit at different times. Speed seems to have nothing to with the interaction which occurs. This does not mean that speed does not exist. It does and is related to p through mv nonrelativistically and $mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ relativistically. The question is whether it affects an interaction because it is the interactions which govern the physics, it seems. For a photon moving along the x axis and hitting a y -axis interface between n_1 and n_2 ($n_2 > n_1$) at $x=0$, speed is not needed at all to solve for the relative probabilities of reflection and refraction. This problem is governed entirely by momentum so one may use $\exp(ipx)$ alone. One may balance $\exp(ipx)$ s at $x=0$ together with the constraint $i p x P(x)$ at $x=0$ as a second equation i.e.

$A+B=C$ ((7b)) and $Ap -Bp=Cp^2$ ((7c)) where A,B,C are linked to the incident, reflected and refracted photons.

No speed appears explicitly in this problem and one does not need to know $E=pc$ in order to find B,C in terms of A, p and p^2 . As a result, this is a very different solution for a steady state problem, which contains motion, from the usual Newtonian approach which is concerned with $x(t)$. One may use $E=pc$ after multiplying ((7b)) and ((7a)) together. This yields a pressure balance equation (as AAp , BBp and CCp^2 are pressures) or a number/energy balance. Such a classical equation bypasses the physics associated with a momentum p in space, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Yet it is $\exp(ipx)$ which describes impulse hits.

In a quantum single particle bound state problem, $\exp(ipx)$ governs the hits with $V(x)$. The particle, however, still has velocity v linked to p. Given that the impulse hits which occur with $V(x)$ also lead to energy imbalance in x, for an overall constant E energy at each x, one must have energy in a different form, namely kinetic energy, which like pressure depends on both p and v i.e. constant pv. The underlying probability, however, is $\exp(ipx)$ because it governs the impulse hits which give rise to velocity.

Two Different Probabilities?

We next consider the quantum mechanical probability $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is usually taken to represent a probability in x. Here $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ for the spatial piece discussed above. Why should one have two probabilities? $\exp(ipx)$ shows the two dimensional probability associated with free motion due to the resistance p (impulse). This is a somewhat complicated probability, but one that is crucial to describing impulse hits which occur due to n-slit experiments, interactions with a $V(x)$ and interactions at an interface of two indices of refraction. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is crucial if direct impulse interactions occur. How does one associate a probability to such a particle? One might argue that the particle treats all x points equally as it spends the same time in each dx. This description completely drops the periodic probability associated with $\exp(ipx)$. The idea of spending the same time in each dx, however, applies to both p and -p. In other words, we argue that the constant x probability scenario should describe a system with both p and -p i.e.

$$P(p)P(-p) = \exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) \quad ((8))$$

This description seems to eliminate physical stochasticity inherent in both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, but describes two steady state streams i.e. average motion. Given that the $i p x P(x)$ constraints cancel for p and -p, one may maximize ((8)) subject to the constraint: $\int P(x)dx=1$. This leads to the usual flipping of a coin or die result.

We note that if one has $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$, $\exp(ipx)$ is the same for both. The product ((8)) is then 1 for half the particles being m_1v_1 and the other half m_2v_2 . The energy factor $\exp(-iEt)$, however, picks out the difference between the two, i.e.

$$\exp(ipx) (\sqrt{.5} \exp(-iE_1t) + \sqrt{.5}\exp(-iE_2t)) \quad ((9))$$

$W^*(x)W(x)$ then leads to an oscillation in time showing the imbalance in the enhanced inertia (i.e. energy) values.

The reason we examine the analysis of $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ is that we think that it removes some of the stochasticity present in the system. This carries over to the bound state situation for which:

$$W^*(x)W(x)=\text{probability in } x \text{ with } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((10))$$

Although $W^*(x)W(x)$ catches the fluctuations due to differences in p , i.e. $\cos(px)$ $2a(p)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$, it loses the inherent fluctuations for each $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ terms a equal 1, when they contain stochastic motion. In other words, using $W^*(x)W(x)$ to create a bound state entropy only captures part of the stochasticity of the system. It is almost as if the difference: $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ipx) = \exp(i(p-p_1)x)$ together with the complex conjugate captures a kind of quasiparticle which creates density variations in x even in the average $v=x/t$ scenario. We argue that these quasiparticle variations are only part of the stochasticity.

We also argue that for the case of $V(x)$, interactions are not linked with time. Average $pp/2m$ which is used for average kinetic energy is linked with time, i.e. $pp/m = pv$ and so is proportional to pressure, but the goal is to establish an average x space balance. It is true that different $\exp(ipx)$ values are associated with different $\exp(-iEt)$, but this creates only microscopic time fluctuations. The sum of $KE(\text{average}) + V(x) = E_n$ constant creates an overall energy which again represents an average resistance i.e. is associated with binding energy, say of an electron in an atom. E_n is an average and so there is no issue with fluctuations due to: $\exp(-iE_1t)\exp(-E_2t)$, where $E_1=p_1p_1/2m$ and $E_2=p_2p_2/2m$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint is composed of two fundamental parts. First, the form $\ln(P(e))$ in $\ln(P(e)) = \text{Lagrange multiplier } G(e)$, where $G(e)$ is the constraint function, ensures that the derivative $d/d e \ln(P(e))$ is of the form: $dP/de / P$. Thus maximization of \ln of the number of permutations contributes specifically to the form $d \ln(P(e))/de$. The constraint, however, is of equal importance. Taking d/de of the maximized entropy yields a balance equation which we argue must be directly linked to mechanical balance in the problem (at least for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas). In other words the constraint seems to be directly linked to a physical resistance. In the MB case, $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ is equivalent to a balance of pressure values for each particle. The constraint is really a mechanical one linked to balance, we argue,

We extend these ideas to the quantum free particle with rest mass (inertia) and its enhanced form E energy being resistances as well as p which is proportional to momentum. We suggest that free particle motion is associated with maximization of Shannons' entropy subject to periodic constraints which yields E and p in the balance equation, i.e. constraints linear in t and x . We further argue that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ creates a system with both p and $-p$ present and only considers average motion. Thus entropy based on 1 as probability is not the same as that associated with $\exp(ipx)$. This seems to be an issue, because $W(x)W(x)$ is used to calculate the

entropy of a quantum single particle bound state, but much of the stochasticity is removed from such an expression. In other words, we argue that Shannon's entropy using $W(x)W(x)$ as probability does not capture the full stochasticity present, but only the quantum quasiparticle type effects while ignoring $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$, i.e. the stochasticity associated with motion.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Energy-Space Statistical Features of the Klein-Gordon Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2023)